

SECTOR-WISE ANALYSIS OF FDI INFLOWS IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Foreign Direct Investment is the nation's economic background, it has long been discussed that Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) plays an momentous role in promoting export and for the renovation of Indian economy. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is well thought-out as a very important means of promoting export of the huge number countries. Foreign direct investment (FDI) in India has predictable improvement from initiate of the Make in India scheme. FDI in sectors activities to the extent permitted under the automatic route does not require any prior approval either of the government or the reserve bank of India. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in activities not covered under the automatic route requires prior approval of the Government which is considered by the Foreign Investment Promotion Board, Department Of Economics Affairs, and Ministry of Finance. In the last decade India has shown a tremendous increase in Foreign Direct Investment into the various sectors in economy. Even though Government of India has made a pathway for attracting FDI on various sectors, this research article focuses on evaluating the FDI inflows through various sectors. This article shows the efforts taken by the government for cheering the FDI into various sectors and the ways through which they are allowed into different sectors of Indian economy. The statistical tools such as Standard Deviation, Covariance and CAGR are used for the analysis.

Key words: FDI, Service sectors, Equity inflow, Cumulative inflow

INTRODUCTION

Indian Economy has been still considered as capital is needed to development and builds the economy of our nation. Hence, a high level of economic growth is not sustainable. At this juncture foreign direct investment is widely recognized as important drive of growth in our country. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) being a non – debt capital flow, is a leading source of external financing, especially for the developing economies. It not only brings in capital and technical know- how but also increase the competitiveness of the economy. Over all its supplements domestic investment, much required for sustaining the high growth rate of the country. Indian Economy is still considered capital scared one. We need long term capital to develop and build the economy. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) plays an important role in the developing economy like India. The polices relating Foreign Direct Investment(FDI) Underwent a major change in July 1991 as a part of the structural adjustment programme in India, under the P.V. Narasima Rao led congress Government. In this paper role of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in retail sector, FDI Equity Inflow, sector wise FDI inflows in India and share of top investing countries FDI inflows in India. In the affirmative augmentation in the estimation of Foreign Direct Investment inflows in observation of various reasons, for instance, the momentous enthusiasm of Indian clients.(Vethirajan C, et.al, 2019)

Apart from being a critical driver of economic growth, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has been a major non-debt financial resource for the economic development of India. Foreign companies invest in India to take advantage of relatively lower wages, special investment privileges like tax exemptions, etc. For a country where foreign investment is being made, it also means achieving technical know-how and generating employment. The Indian Government's favorable policy regime and robust business environment has ensured that foreign capital keeps flowing into the country. The Government has taken many initiatives in recent years such as relaxing FDI norms across sectors such as defense, Public Sector Unit oil refineries, telecom, power exchanges, and stock exchanges, among others.

Market size

According to the Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade (DPIIT), FDI equity inflow in India stood at US\$ 521.47 billion between April 2000 and December 2020, indicating that the government's efforts to improve ease of doing business and relaxing FDI norms have yield results.

FDI equity inflows in India stood at US\$ 51.47 billion in 2020-21 (between April 2020 and December 2020). Data for 2020-21 indicates that the computer software and hardware sector attracted the highest FDI equity inflows of US\$ 24.39 billion, followed by the construction (infrastructure) activities (US\$ 7.15 billion), service sector (US\$ 3.86 billion) and trading (US\$ 2.14 billion).

In 2020-21 (between April 2020 and December 2020), India received the highest FDI equity inflows from Singapore (US\$ 15.72 billion), followed by the US (US\$ 12.83 billion), the UAE (US\$ 3.92 billion), Mauritius (US\$ 3.48 billion), Cayman Islands (US\$ 2.53 billion), the Netherlands (US\$ 2.44 billion) and the UK (US\$ 1.83 billion).

In 2020-21 (between April 2020 and December 2020), Gujarat received the highest FDI equity inflows of US\$ 21.24 billion, followed by Maharashtra (US\$ 13.64 billion), Karnataka (US\$ 6.37 billion) and Delhi (US\$ 4.22 billion).

Investments/ Developments

Some of the significant FDI announcements made recently are as follows:

- In the first nine months of FY21, total FDI inflows amounted to US\$ 67.54 billion, a 22% YoY increase.
- In February 2021, Amazon announced to start manufacturing electronic devices in India from 2021
- In January 2021, Amazon partnered with Startup India, Sequoia Capital India and Fireside Ventures to launch an accelerator programme to support early-stage start-ups take their brands to international markets and boost domestic exports.
- In November 2020, Rs. 2,480 crore (US\$ 337.53 million) foreign direct investment (FDI) in ATC Telecom Infra Pvt Ltd. was approved by the Union Cabinet.

- In November 2020, Amazon Web Services (AWS) announced to invest US\$ 2.77 billion (Rs. 20,761 crore) in Telangana to set up multiple data centres; this is the largest FDI in the history of the state.
- Since April 2020, the government has received over 120 foreign direct investment (FDI) proposals worth ~Rs. 12,000 crore (US\$ 1.63 billion) from China. Between April 2000 and September 2020, India received US\$ 2.43 billion FDI from China.
- According to the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), India's Outward Foreign Direct Investments (OFDIs) in equity, loan and guaranteed issue stood at ~US\$ 1.85 billion in February 2021 vs. US\$ 1.19 billion in January 2021.

Government Initiatives

In March 2021, the parliament approved a bill to increase foreign direct investment (FDI) in the insurance sector from 49% to 74%. In March 2021, Mr. Shripad Naik, the Minister of State for Defence, stated that a total of 44 Indian companies, including public sector units, have received approvals related to FDI for joint production of defence items with foreign organizations. In December 2020, the government of Uttar Pradesh agreed to provide Samsung Display Noida Private Limited with special incentives to set up a mobile and IT display product manufacturing unit. The Government of India is huge to accomplish US\$ 100 billion worth of FDI inflows in the going with 2020. The World Bank has referenced that private part premiums in India are predicted to make by 8.8 percent in F 2018-2019 to be more than private utilization progression of 7.4 percent, and in this manner drive the improvement in India's Gross Domestic Product in FY 2018-2019 according to information concern (Vethirajan, et.al, 2019). Under the Central Government's Scheme for Promotion of Manufacturing Electronic Components and Semiconductors (SPECES), Samsung will also receive a financial incentive of Rs. 460 crore (US\$ 62.61 million). This project will develop a global export hub in Uttar Pradesh and will help the state attract more Foreign Direct Investments (FDI). In December 2020, changes in the guidelines for the provision of Direct-to-Home (DTH) services have been approved by the Union Cabinet, enabling 100% FDI in the DTH broadcasting services market.

Road ahead

India is expected to attract Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) of US\$ 120-160 billion per year by 2025, according to CII and EY report. Over the past 10 years, the country witnessed a 6.8% rise in GDP with FDI increasing to GDP at 1.8%. In terms of attractiveness, investors ranked India #3; ~80% investors have plans to invest in India in the next upcoming years, while 25% reported investments worth >US\$ 500 million, the Economic Times reported.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Renju Joseph (2018), Discussed the Impact of FDI Inflows in Balance of Payment. He has main objective of the study is to show the relation current account and balance of trade and capital account FDI and how its effect on balance of payment of country. The concluded that there is a significant association of current account to the balance of trade with beta value as 1.04, regression value is 0.987 with significance value 0.000 this implies that the balance of trade has a strong impact of current account. Currently the current account is deficit but on a declining mode. Balance of trade having a strong association can be used as a major tool to control the deficit and decrees the deficit.

D.Ramesh &S. Packialakshmi (2014), in their paper namely “the pros and cons of foreign direct investment in India” In this study concluded that in India is need to put in place a comprehensive development strategy, which includes being open to trade and FDI. This should go a long way in fulfilling that the ultimate goal of permanently eradicating poverty.

Narayana (2012), explained that one of the major concerns of planners and policy makers in India is attracting more and more Foreign Direct Investment. He analyzed the Foreign Direct Investment and its flows into India. He highlighted the basic constraints to investment in general and Foreign Direct Investment in particular.

Juan Pineiro et. al (2008), in the Paper namely “Does Growth and Quality of Capital markets Drive Foreign capital? - The case of cross-. Border M and As” examined the association between the quantum of FDI in a firm and the quality of capital market growth of that firm. The period of study was from 1987 to 2006. After a comparative study of “both the stock market variables and the financial and regulatory reforms variables, they observed that the coefficients was higher than other variables. They concluded that higher reforms in capital markets may result into higher increase in firm level Foreign Direct Investment”. Moreover, the results are found to be enormously forceful when they “replaced stock market variables with squared values of the

same, reconfirming the fact that bigger is the escalation, better is the inflow of firm level Foreign Direct Investment.”

Objectives of the study

The following are the objectives of the prospective study.

1. To study the new FDI policy in India and Cumulative FDI inflows in to India
2. To analysis of Route Wise FDI inflows in India
3. To exhibit the sectors wise and year wise attracting FDI inflows.

Methodology

This research is descriptive study in nature. The data has been collected from the secondary sources such as books, news paper published and unpublished reports and working paper in the internet particularly from the Department of industrial and promotion, ministry of commerce and industry and the like. Besides the data have been analyzed by using the simple tool of percentage analysis, mean, standard deviation, co-efficient variation and compound annual growth rate.

Period of the study

In this paper, the study period covers three financial years' starts from April, 2018 and ends with March, 2021.

TABLE 1

Cumulative FDI inflows in to India during the period 2000 - 2021

S.No	Particulars	Amount of FDI inflows	
		(Rs. in Crore)	US \$ million
1.	Cumulative FDI inflows	-	763576
2.	Cumulative FDI equity inflow	3174480	529633
3	Amount of FDI equity inflows during the financial year 2020-21	59514	8165
4.	Amount of Total equity inflows during the financial year 2020-2021	-	13438

Source: Fact sheet FDI. RBI April 2000 – March -20201

Table 1 depicts that the amount of FDI inflows from April 2000 to March 2021. It shows the cumulative amount of FDI inflows both in terms of crore and US \$ million. The first part shows the sum of equity inflows, reinvested earnings and other capital. Cumulative amount of inflows are 763576 in US \$ million. Other than this cumulative FDI equity inflows which excludes amount remitted through RBI s NRI schemes are 3174480 in crore and 529633 in US \$ million, FDI inflows during 2020-2021 (March ,2021) the first part shows the sum of equity inflows, reinvested earnings and other capital. The total amount of inflows are 13438 in US \$ million. The second part shows that the FDI equity inflows amounted 59514 in crore and 8165 in US \$.

TABLE 2

FDI EQUITY INFLOWS (MONTH- WISE) DURING THE PERIOD 2020 – 2021

S.No	Financial year 2020-2021	Amount of FDI equity inflows	
		(In Rs. Crore)	US \$ million
1.	April, 2020	21,133	2,772
2.	May, 2020	16,951	2,240
3.	June, 2020	11,736	1,550
4.	July, 2020	22,866	3,049
5	August, 2020	1,30,576	17,487
6	September, 2020	21,350	2,906
7	October,2020	39,160	5,331
8	November, 2020	63,196	8,515
9	December, 2020	56,086	7,621
10	January, 2021	19,790	2,707
11	February,2021	18,822	2,587
12	March,2021	20,903	2,872
13	2020-2021(from April, 2020 March, 2021)	4,42,569	59,636
14	2019-2020(from April, 2019 to March, 2020)	353558	49977
15	Percentage growth over last year	(+)25%	(+)19%
	Regression co-efficient(R)	0.043	

	R²	0.0018	
	F- Value	0.018	
	P-Value	0.9	
	Remarks	p-value $\geq \alpha$ (0.05), we accept the H ₀	

Source: Fact sheet FDI. RBI April 2000 – March -2021

The above table 2 shows the amount of FDI inflows during financial year from April, 2020 to March 2021. It shows the amount in Rs. crore and in US \$ mn. The highest FDI inflow in the country is in the month of August 2020 , 1,30,576 in Rs crore and 17,487 in us \$ mn. Flowed by November, 2020 and, November 2020 with inflows 63,196 in Rs, crore (8,515 in us \$ mn) and December 2020, 56,086 in Rs crore(7,621 in us \$ mn) respect. It can also be observed that there in 25% growth over last year. The R square shows that during this periods FDI variance in the equity inflows was 0.043 (43 per cent), significant at 5 per cent level of significance and F value is 0.018

Table 3
Sector wise FDI equity inflows in India during April 2018 to March, 2021

(Rupees in Crores (US % million)

Ran ks	Sector	2018- 2019 April- March	2019- 2020 April- March	2020- 2021 April- March	MEAN	S.D	C.V	CAGR %
1.	Service Sector	63,909 (9,158)	55,429 (7,854)	37,542 (5,060)	52293	13460	0.257	-16.25
2.	Computer Software and Hardware	45,297 (6,415)	54,250 (7,673)	1,94,291 (26,145)	97946	83557	0.853	62.48
3.	Telecommunicati ons'	18,337 (2,668)	30,940 (4,445)	2,884 (392)	17387	14052	0.808	-46.02
4.	Trading	30,963 (4,462)	32,406 (4,574)	19,349 (2,608)	27572	7158	0.259	-14.51
5.	Constructions Development	1,503 ((213)	4,350 (617)	3,117 (422)	2990	1428	0.477	27.52
6.	Automobile Industry	18,309 (1,981)	19753 (1,058)	12,115 (1,637)	16726	4058	0.242	-12.86
7.	Construction (infrastructure)	15,927 (2,258)	14,510 (2,042)	58,240 (7,875)	29559	20289	0.686	54.06

8	Chemicals	13,685 (1981)	7,492 (1058)	6,300 (847)	9159	3237	0.353	-22.79
9.	Drugs and Pharmaceuticals	1,842 (266)	3,650 (518)	11,015 (1,490)	5502	3967	0.721	81.51
10.	Hotel and Tourism	7,590 (1,076)	21,060 (2,938)	2,761 (369)	10470	7743	0.740	28.61

Source: www.dipp.gov/fdi-statisticatilfigure-India - FDI April 2000 to March, 2021.

From the above Table 3 of research methodology clearly depicts a sector wise FDI equity inflow in India during the period of April, 2018 to March, 2021, the mean value of sector wise FDI in computer software and hardware has highest mean (97946) and construction has the lowest mean (2990) . The compound annual growth rate of return on sector wise FDI inflow is positive in case of Drugs and pharmaceuticals (81.51) and rest of other sector like as telecommunication has lowest compound annual growth rate (-46.02), and the rest of other sector shown negative during the period 2018-2019to 2020-2021 up to March.

Findings of the Study

1) FDI is an important stimulus for the economic growth of India. 2) Drugs and pharmaceuticals is first and computer and software is second segment of which pick the growth (CAGR) in second decade of reforms 3) FDI creates high perks jobs for skilled employee in Indian service sector. 4) The highest amount 59,636 million dollars of FDI in India came from the financial year 2020-2021

Suggestions

The following Suggestions are proposed: The government should make polices transparent, where in the foreign investors gain positive attitude of investing in India. The policy changes in the entry and exit of FDI based on the flow and its impact has to be considered. Government should encourage companies to invest overseas in the form of equity and loans instead of guarantee. Sectors such as medical services should be liberalized for affected by covid

19 in all the country during the period from 2019 to till the date. FDI plays an important role in the development of infrastructure because many countries invest in the infrastructure sector and service and banking finance sectors.

Conclusion

In India FDI plays a pivotal role in Indian economy through its constitution to transfer of knowledge and improvement of technologies create employment through the development of different regions. The Government of India is recently increased the limit of FDI in different sector. However there are many hindrance in the way of FDI inflow and dominate in the majority National ruling party. Government should take final decision in the field of FDI in particular sector cannot interpret in other ruling part. If above pointed out done on a priority basis FDI will be import role in the development of our country.

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